

Aloidendron pillansii

Giant Quiver tree

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 10m

Distribution:

The Giant Quiver Tree is confined to the northwestern part of South Africa and southern part of Namibia. There are three subpopulations, one that occurs in Namibia around Rosh Pinah, a second from the central Richtersveld area, and a third around Eksteenfontein in the southern parts of the Richtersveld. Most of the individuals occur within the AïAis/Richtersveld Transfrontier Park.

Importance:

These plants are valued for their age, resilience, and strong association with the Richtersveld, and are highly sought after for their architectural form, increasing their trade value in arid regions. Populations are declining due to illegal collection, mining-related habitat loss and degradation, and growing human pressure. Prolonged droughts, likely intensified by climate change, have caused mortality and increased baboon predation, posing major ongoing threats.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 345.06 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 5.63 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 12.24 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 97.6% [Single: 88.2%, Duplicated: 9.4%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 492.02 kilobases

Contig number: 49 838

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